

Structure, antimicrobial activity and molecular docking study of novel *o*-vaniline based sulfamethoxazolyl derivatives[†]

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Abstract : Four sulfamethoxazolyl-azo Schiff bases, SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-R) (Sulfamethoxazole, SMX; R = H (2a), -CH₃ (2b), -Cl (2c), -OCH₃ (2d)) have been prepared by the condensation of SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO) (1) with R-C₆H₄-NH₂. The compounds are characterized by spectroscopic studies (FT-IR, UV-Vis, Mass, NMR). The structural confirmation has been carried out by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies in one case, SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)-C=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃ (2b). The supramolecular 1D chain is constituted by inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonds and also by π --- π interaction of aromatic rings. The antibacterial properties have been evaluated against Gram-positive bacteria. Most favored binding mode of the drugs with the active site residues of DHPS (dihydropteroate synthetase) is established by *in silico* Molecular Docking using Discovery studio 3.5 software.

Keywords : Sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-imine derivatives, *o*-vanillin, X-ray structure, DFT, antimicrobial activity, molecular docking.

Introduction

Antibiotics are used as life-saving drugs since the discovery of penicillin in 1928¹. Recently, antibiotic resistance is a common incident². Consequently, design of newer antibiotics derived from conventional antibiotics by chemical functionalization is becoming extremely urgent^{3,4}. Therefore, search of more effective and low toxic drugs has taken fantastic impetus in the area of synthetic and pharmaceutical chemistry⁵. Azo compounds show a variety of interesting biological activities such as, antineoplastics, antidiabetics, antiseptics, anti-HIV and other useful chemotherapeutic properties⁶. Schiff bases are one of the most exten-

sively used organic compounds and divulge a wide collection of biological activities^{7,8} such as, anti-fungal^{9,10}, antibacterial^{11,12}, antiproliferative, antimalarial^{13,14} and antipyretic. Therefore, sulfonamides consisting of both azo (-N=N-) and imine (-C=N-) functions may serve as challenging molecules in the medicinal and pharmaceutical fields^{15,16}.

Sulfonamide (-SO₂NH-), an antibacterial, anti-tumor, anti-viral, anti-fungal, diuretic, antithyroid, hypoglycaemic etc. hinder the synthesis of folic acid. Folate, useful agent for synthesis and regulation of nucleic acids (DNA, RNA) in the cells, is synthesized by direct participation of DHPS in a

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catalytic cycle¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Due to structural analogy of sulfonamides, C₆H₄(COOH)(*p*-NH₂) (*p*-aminobenzoic acid, PABA) inhibits dihydropteroate synthetase (DHPS), hence regulates proliferation and growth of bacteria. However, prolonged administration of sulfonamide causes many undesirable effects including liver disease, kidney injury, skin rashes, drug fever, lung infection and hemolytic anemia²⁰⁻²². These toxicity and antibiotic resistance can be regulated by the functionalization of sulfonamides. In continuation of our research, herein, we have designed a new series of sulfonamides consisting of both azo and imine functions²³⁻²⁷. *o*-Vaniline, a natural aldehyde found in *Andropogon nardus*²⁸ and used for the treatment of sickle cell disease (SCD)²⁹, is coupled with diazonium salt of sulphamethoxazole (SMX-N=N⁺) to synthesize SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO) (**1**) which is then condensed with *p*-R-C₆H₄-NH₂ to isolate azo-imine functionalized sulfonamides, SMX-N=N-C₂H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-R) (R = H (**2a**), -CH₃ (**2b**), -Cl (**2c**), -OCH₃ (**2d**)). Following different spectroscopic techniques the molecules **2**, have been characterized along with single crystal X-ray structure of one of the derivatives. The DFT computation has been performed to explain the electronic structure and spectra. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds has been evaluated against several standard Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial stain. Docking of these molecules with DHPS protein has been focused to investigate the most preferred binding mode and hence the plausible mechanism of antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Materials and methods

Sulfamethoxazole was purchased from Hi-Media. Sodium nitrite, sodium hydroxide, were available from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., *o*-vaniline, aniline, toluene, anicidine, *p*-chloroaniline were purchased from Aldrich, and other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade purified by standard procedure³⁰.

Physical measurements

Microanalytical data (C, H, and N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra were collected from Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model Lambda 25; FTIR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were assembled from Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer model RX-1; the ¹H NMR spectra were obtained from Bruker (AC) 300/500 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. ESI mass spectra were recorded on a micro mass Q-TOF mass spectrometer (Serial no. YA 263). Antimicrobial activity is performed by the Gram-positive bacteria strain.

Synthesis of 4-((3-formyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl)diazenyl)-N-(5-methyl isoxazol-3-yl)benzene-sulfonamide (**1**)

Dropwise addition of ice cold aqueous solution (0–5 °C) of sodium nitrite (0.272 g, 3.95 mmol) to cold 3(*N*) 18 ml HCl solution of sulphamethoxazole (SMX, 1.0 g, 3.95 mmol) formed sulfamethoxazolyl diazonium (SMX-N=N⁺) salt and it was kept for 25 min. Then the diazotized product was added dropwise to the cold sodium hydroxide (2.4 g) solution of *o*-vaniline (0.60 g, 3.95 mmol) with continuous stirring; yellow precipitate appeared at pH 7 (Scheme 1) which was filtered and dried. Then it was re-crystallized from aqueous methanol solution by slow evaporation. For further purification the column chromatography was performed (in silica gel, 60–120 mesh) and the desired product was eluted with 1 : 10 (v/v), petroleum ether (60–80)-ethylacetate eluent. The isolated yield was 68%.

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO), **1**, C₁₈H₁₆N₄O₆S (M.W. 416.4) : m.p, 218 °C Microanalytical data : Calcd. C, 51.92; H, 3.87; N, 13.45; Found : C, 51.84; H, 3.93; N, 13.38%; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹); ν(C-O), 1084; ν(N=N), 1453; ν(C-N), 1616; ν(O-H), 3438; ν(S-O), 1176. (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S1); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ (17-CH₃)(oxazole) 2.38 (s); δ(16-H), 8.02 (s); δ(O-H), 11.66 (s); δ(N-H), 6.27 (s); δ(CH-N) 10.05 (s); δ(-OCH₃)(vaniline) 4.04(s); δ(5-H), 7.72 (s);

$\delta(7\text{-H})$, 7.75(s); $\delta(10,12\text{-H})$, 7.99 (d, $J=3.48$); $\delta(9,13\text{-H})$, 7.95 (d, $J=2.13$) ppm (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S2). Mass (m/z), $(M+Na)^+$ (439.06) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S3). UV-Vis spectroscopic data in MeOH ($\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})(10^{-4} \in (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}))$) : 265 (2.67), 388 (2.19).

Azo sulfonamide Schiff bases, SMX-N=N-C₆H₃(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-Ar), 2 (Ar = -C₆H₅ (2a), -C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃ (2b), C₆H₄-*p*-Cl (2c), -C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃ (2d))

To hot ethanol solution of **1** (0.1 g, 0.24 mmol) was refluxed with Ar-NH₂ (0.30 mmol) and refluxed for 5 to 10 h. The solution was then allowed to evaporate slowly in air and orange yellow crystals were deposited on glass wall. The crystals were collected and TLC test was performed to check purity. The product, SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-Ar), **2** (Ar = -C₆H₅ (2a), -C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃ (2b), C₆H₄-*p*-Cl (2c), -C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃ (2d)), was recrystallized from methanol solution. The yield was 63–72%.

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₅), C₂₄H₂₁N₅O₅S (**2a**) (M.W. 491.5) (yield, 68%), m.p. 240 °C. Calcd. : C, 58.64; H, 4.30; N, 14.25; Found : C, 58.73; H, 4.25; N, 14.21%. IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1128, $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 1493, $\nu(\text{N=N})$; 1618, $\nu(\text{C=N})$; 3068, $\nu(\text{O-H})$; 1165, $\nu(\text{SO}_2)$; (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S4); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) $\delta(17\text{-CH}_3)(\text{oxazole})$ 2.29 (s); $\delta(\text{O-H})$, 10.37 (s); $\delta(\text{N-H})$, 6.16 (s); $\delta(\text{CH-N})$ 9.21 (s); $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)(\text{vaniline})$ 3.95(s); $\delta(16\text{-H})$, 7.99 (s); $\delta(5\text{H, phenyl protons of aniline, merged})$ 8.00 ppm, $\delta(2\text{H, phenyl protons of benzene ring of SMX})$ 7.53 ppm (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S5). UV-Vis spectroscopic data in MeOH ($\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})(10^{-4} \in (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}))$) : 226 (6.73), 381 (2.42). Mass (m/z), $(M+Na)^+$ (414.12) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S6).

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃), C₂₅H₂₃N₅O₅S (**2b**) (M.W. 505.53) (yield, 72%), m.p. 222 °C. Calcd. C, 59.39; H, 4.58; N, 13.85; Found : C, 60.56; H, 4.40; N, 14.01%. IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1128, $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 1466,

$\nu(\text{N=N})$; 1622, $\nu(\text{C=N})$; 3445, $\nu(\text{O-H})$; 1173, $\nu(\text{S-O})$ (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S7). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) $\delta(17\text{-CH}_3)(\text{oxazole})$ 2.29 (s); $\delta(21\text{-CH}_3)(\text{toluidine})$ 2.34; $\delta(16\text{-H})$, 7.99 (s); $\delta(\text{O-H})$, 12.12 (s); $\delta(\text{N-H})$, 6.15 (s); $\delta(\text{CH-N})$ 9.20 (s); $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)(\text{vaniline})$ 3.94(s) $\delta(6\text{H, phenyl protons})$ 7.99 ppm, $\delta(3\text{H, phenyl protons})$ 7.44–7.50 ppm $\delta(2\text{H, phenyl protons})$ 7.32 ppm (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S8). UV-Vis spectroscopic data in MeOH ($\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})(10^{-4} \in (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}))$) : 226 (7.66), 379 (2.00). Mass (m/z), $(M+Na)^+$ (528.10) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S9).

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-Cl), C₂₄H₂₀N₅O₅SCl (**2c**) (M.W. 525.89) (yield, 67%) : m.p. 230 °C. Calcd. : C, 59.39; H, 4.58; N, 13.85; Found : C, 59.56; H, 4.49; N, 14.01%. IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1128, $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 1464, $\nu(\text{N=N})$; 1617, $\nu(\text{C=N})$; 3450, $\nu(\text{O-H})$; 1172, $\nu(\text{S-O})$ (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S10). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) $\delta(17\text{-CH}_3)(\text{oxazole})$ 2.29 (s); $\delta(16\text{-H})$, 7.99 (s); $\delta(\text{O-H})$, 12.14(s); $\delta(\text{N-H})$, 6.16 (s); $\delta(\text{CH-N})$ 9.18 (s); $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)(\text{vaniline})$ 3.94(s) $\delta(6\text{H, phenyl protons})$ 8.00 ppm, $\delta(4\text{H, phenyl protons})$ 7.50 ppm (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S11). UV-Vis spectroscopic data in MeOH ($\lambda_{\max}(\text{nm})(10^{-4} \in (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}))$) : 226 (11.18), 381 (3.05). Mass (m/z), $(M+Na)^+$ (549.12) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S12).

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃), C₂₅H₂₃N₅O₆S (**2d**) (M.W. 521.52) (yield, 63%), m.p. 248 °C. Calcd. : C, 57.57; H, 4.83; N, 13.43; Found : C, 57.45; H, 4.75; N, 13.40% by wt. IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1128, $\nu(\text{C-O})$; 1466, $\nu(\text{N=N})$; 1617, $\nu(\text{C=N})$; 3417, $\nu(\text{O-H})$; 1172, $\nu(\text{S-O})$. (Supplementary Materials, Fig. 13). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) $\delta(17\text{-CH}_3)(\text{oxazole})$ 2.29 (s); $\delta(16\text{-H})$, 7.98 (s); $\delta(\text{O-H})$, 10.27 (s); $\delta(\text{N-H})$, 6.22 (s); $\delta(\text{CH-N})$ 8.67 (s); $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)(\text{vaniline})$ 4.00 (s); $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)(\text{toluidine})$ 3.85(s); $\delta(16\text{-H})$, 7.73 (s); $\delta(4\text{H, 19,20,22,23 phenyl protons})$ 7.98 ppm; $\delta(10,12\text{-H})$, 7.35 (d, $J=7.88$); $\delta(9,13\text{-H})$, 7.00 (d, $J=8.07$) ppm; $\delta(7\text{-H})$ 7.73 (s) ppm; $\delta(5\text{-H})$ 7.56 (s) ppm (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S14).

UV-Vis spectroscopic data in MeOH (λ_{\max} (nm)($10^{-1} \in (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1})$)) : 233 (10.86), 378 (2.00). Mass (m/z), ($M+\text{Na}$)⁺ (544.15) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S15).

X-Ray crystal structure analysis of SMX-N=N-C₆H₃(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃), (2b)

The crystal of **2b** was formed by the slow evaporation of methanol solution ($0.12 \times 0.10 \times 0.02 \text{ mm}^3$) for a week. Data were collected (Table 1) by Rigaku Saturn 724+ CCD diffractometer with a Mo-K α ; radiation source (Wavelength = 0.71075 Å) at 150 K under continuous flow of cooled nitrogen gas with θ in the range $2.363 \leq \theta \leq 24.999$ and $h k l$ range : $-18 \leq h \leq 18$, $-23 \leq k \leq 23$, $-19 \leq l \leq 17$. The data collection, integration and indexing were performed using Crystalclear-SM software and a numerical method was employed to correct for absorption. All the calculations were carried out using the programs in WinGX module and the structure solution was solved by direct methods using SIR-92³¹. The final refinement of the structure was carried out using full least-square methods on F² using SHELX-14³². All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were refined isotropically as rigid atoms in their idealized locations. Crystallographic refinement data are collected in Table 1. Residual minimum and maximum electron densities are -0.350 and 0.440.

Antimicrobial activity

[SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO)] (**1**) and its four derivatives SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₅) (**2a**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃) (**2b**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-Cl) (**2c**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃) (**2d**) were tested against Gram-positive, *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633). The solution of the compounds were prepared by HPLC grade DMSO; final % of DMSO during assay was varied from 0.5–0.8% although the main stocks solution of the drugs were pre-

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement of SMX-N=N-C₆H₃(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃) (**2b**)

2b	
Empirical formula	C ₅₀ H ₄₆ N ₁₀ O ₁₀ S ₂
Formula weight	1011.09
Temperature (K)	150 (2)
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 2 ₁ /c
<i>a</i> (Å)	15.806(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	19.565(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.462(3)
α (°)	90
β (°)	106.932(3)
γ (°)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	4870.1(15)
<i>Z</i>	4
μ (Mo-K α (mm ⁻¹))	0.180
θ range	2.363–24.999
<i>D</i> _{calc} (mg m ⁻³)	1.379
Refine parameters	657
Total reflections	36488
Unique reflections	8557
R_1^a [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0522 (8159)
wR_2^b	0.1333 (8557)
GOF ^c	1.124
Difference between peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	0.711, -0.503
$a^a R = \sum F_0 - F_c / \sum F_0$. $b^b wR = [\sum w(F_0^2 - F_c^2) / \sum w F_0^4]^{1/2}$ are general but <i>w</i> are different, $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_0^2) + (0.0508P)^2 + 1.7997P]$ where $P = (F_0^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

pared using spectroscopic grade DMSO and stored at -20 °C. All the bacterial strains were inoculated in a freshly prepared autoclaved LB broth from a 24 h old LA slant and kept in shaker for overnight. The final bacterial count was 1×10^4 cells/ml with sterile LB by dilution and the overnight culture. The diluted culture was distributed in a number of tubes and incubated in absence and in presence of test compounds. Now the tubes were incubated for 16–18 h at 37 °C with continuous shaking. The OD₆₀₀ had been measured in a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu). The 100% growth of bacterial species had been considered in absence of test ligands. The OD at 600 nm were measured for each concentration incubated under similar experimental condition and

compared to control the relative degree of bacterial growth inhibition had been calculated. The concentration of test compound required to inhibit the growth of bacteria by 50% had been calculated from the % reduction of bacterial growth in comparison to control (The minimum inhibitory concentrations i.e. IC₅₀).

Molecular docking studies of the ligand with DHPS and ADMET

The structures of proteins of DHPS (Dihydroptorate Synthase of *Versinia pestis*, PDB ID 3TZF) were downloaded from the RCSB protein data bank (<http://www.pdb.org>) and used for docking. Sulfamethoxazole, 6-hydroxymethylpterin-diphosphate and magnesium ion were co-crystallized with enzyme. Using CDOCKER Receptor-Ligand interactions protocol section of Discovery Studio client 3.5³³ in the *in silico* docking module all the calculations were performed. Interaction energies between ligands and receptor were recorded. The optimized structures of the compounds (**1**, **2a-d**) have been used for docking study. Ligand preparation was done using prepare ligand module and protein preparation was done under Prepare Protein module in Receptor-Ligand interactions tool of Discovery studio 3.5 and prepared ligand was used for docking. The active site was selected based on the ligand binding domain of sulfamethoxazole then the pre-existing ligand was removed and prepared ligands, were placed. The CDOCKER protocol was used for docking calculations and a grid box centered at the geometrical center of co-crystallized ligand was used. The coordinates x, y, z for the center of grid box were 41.78 Å, 8.05 Å, 2.24 Å and -77.56 Å, 85.05 Å, 93.95 Å respectively. Minimum free energy of protein-ligand complex module was used to select the most favorable docked pose and analyzed to investigate the interaction. Absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion and toxicity (ADMET) prediction were done in ADMET descriptor module of small molecules protocol of Discovery studio client 3.5. Druglikeness of the prepared ligands

were checked following Lipinski's rule of five^{34,35}. Using ADMET module of small molecule protocol of Discovery studio 3.5 software ADMET properties and toxicity of the compounds were checked.

Computational studies

The geometry optimization of **1** and **2a-d** were carried out using Density Functional Theory (DFT) at the B3LYP level³⁶. All calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 program package³⁷ with the aid of the GaussView visualization program³⁸. For C, H, N, O the 6-31G(d) basis set were assigned and the calculations for molecular orbitals were carried out as before³⁸⁻⁴⁰ with the aid of the GaussView visualization program^{41,42}. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. The electronic excitations were computed using the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism in methanol using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)⁴³⁻⁴⁵ GaussSum was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital⁴⁶.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterisation

Sulfamethoxazolyl diazonium ion (SMX-N=N⁺) is coupled with *o*-vaniline at pH 7 to prepare 4-((3-formyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl) diazenyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl) benzene sulfonamide [SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO)] (**1**) which undergoes condensation reaction with aromatic amines *p*-R-C₆H₄-NH₂ to synthesize SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m'*-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-R) (R = H (**2a**), -CH₃ (**2b**), -Cl (**2c**), -OCH₃ (**2d**)) (Scheme 1). In infra-red spectrum of **1** the presence of strong stretch at 1653 cm⁻¹ confirms ν(CHO) which disappears and emerges a new stretch at 1610–1625 cm⁻¹ in **2** which refers to ν(C=N) and supports the condensation reaction. Other significant stretches are ν(N=N), 1470–1480; ν(C-O), 1090–1110; ν(SO₂),

1170–1180 cm^{-1} in support of the synthesis of the compounds (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S4, S7, S10, S13). All the compounds show absorption band at 370–390 nm and 220–270 nm due to $n\text{-}\pi^*$ and $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions, respectively (Fig. 1). The ^1H NMR spectra show very complex pattern in aromatic zone due to large number of proton signals from aromatic rings (atom numbering is given in the structures, Scheme 1); however significant signals such as, oxazolyl- CH_3 (2.45–2.50 ppm), $\delta(\text{OH})$ (10.00–12.50 ppm), $\delta(\text{NH})$ (6.10–6.20 ppm); $\delta(\text{CH}=\text{N})$, 8.10–9.20 ppm, $\delta(-\text{OCH}_3)$ (vaniline) 4.00–3.90 ppm, oxazolyl-H (16-H, singlet) 8.29–8.31 ppm support the structure of the

compounds. Besides, sulfonamide-phenyl-Hs (9,10,12,13-H) become visible as two doublets at 7.35–7.45 ppm. Azophenolato-H such as 7-H is a singlet at 7.10–7.15 ppm while 4,5-H show doublet signal at 7.10–7.30 ppm. The terminal six member ring, arylamine has four or five-Hs and have shown noteworthy signal movement due to substituent effect; electron donating $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{OCH}_3$ influence 21,23-H to shift to upfield side while electron withdrawing groups $-\text{Cl}$ influence them to move to downfield side (Supplementary Materials; Figs. S2, S5, S8, S11, S14). The single crystal structure of **1b** confirms the proposal from other spectroscopic information.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of SMX-azo-imine derivatives; SMX- $\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(p\text{-OH})(m'\text{-OCH}_3)(m\text{-CHO})$ (**1**), SMX- $\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(p\text{-OH})(m'\text{-OCH}_3)(m\text{-CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$ (**2a**), SMX- $\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(p\text{-OH})(m'\text{-OCH}_3)(m\text{-CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}p\text{-CH}_3)$ (**2b**), SMX- $\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(p\text{-OH})(m'\text{-OCH}_3)(m\text{-CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}p\text{-Cl})$ (**2c**), SMX- $\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_2(p\text{-OH})(m'\text{-OCH}_3)(m\text{-CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}p\text{-OCH}_3)$ (**2d**).

Fig. 1. UV-Vis Spectra of 1, 2a-d in MeOH.

Crystal structure description of 2b

The compound **2b** has been crystallized in monoclinic crystal system and $P 2_1/c$ space group. The asymmetric unit of the crystal lattice is constituted of two molecules and these are structurally comparable. A view of the diad including the atom numbering scheme is shown (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S16). A single molecule is shown in Fig. 2 and selected bond parameters are listed in Table 2. In terms of bond distances, angles, as well as gross geometry, these two molecules are closely akin to one another.

The four part of the structure are imine phenolato (A-ring), aryl-sulfonamide (B-ring),

Fig. 2. ORTEP view of the crystal structure of **2b** (Black C; Red O; Blue N; Yellow S and Pink H) (A, B, C, D are ring abbreviation for brevity).

oxazoly ring (C-ring), methyl substitute phenyl (D-ring). The C-ring is linked to B-ring by the sulfonamide (-NH-SO₂-) group in sulfamethoxazole part and the -N=N- group of B-ring is connected to A-ring and A-ring is attached to D-ring by -HC=N- group. The -C₆H₃(OH)(OCH₃)- (A-ring) and -C₆H₄(SO₂)- (B-ring) are bonded by -N=CH- and make dihedral 15.88(13)^o; oxazoly ring (C-ring) is inclined at 88.16(17)^o with B-ring. The N=N azo length is 1.260(3) Å and the C=N imine length is 1.309(3) Å who are closer to the reported data²³⁻²⁷. The results indicate that the bond strength between azo-N and substituted phenol and imine bond is stronger than that of azo-N and sulfonamide-phenyl. In **2b** the supramolecular aggregation takes place through hydrogen bonding (NH...O) and non-classical interaction S-O...CH. (Fig. 3). There are three different mode of CH...π interaction in **2b** which is viewed in Fig. 3. The CH...π distances in the three different forms are respectively C-H(25)C...Ar 2.774 Å (form 1); C-H(1B)...Ar 2.903 Å (form 2); C-H(1C)...Ar, 2.420 Å (form 2); C-H(50B)...Ar 3.428 Å (form 3) and C-H(42B)...Ar 2.880 Å (form 3). The selective bond lengths are S1-N2, 1.654 Å; N3-N4, 1.271 Å; N8-N9, 1.260 Å; C18-N5, 1.310 Å and C43-N10, 1.309 Å (Table 2).

Antimicrobial activity

The compound [SMX-N=N-C₆H₂-(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CHO)] (**1**) and its four Schiff bases SMX-N=N-C₆H₂-(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₅) (**2a**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂-(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-CH₃) (**2b**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂-(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-Cl) (**2c**), SMX-N=N-C₆H₂-(*p*-OH)(*m*'-OCH₃)(*m*-CH=N-C₆H₄-*p*-OCH₃) (**2d**) have been tested against Gram-positive, *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633). The IC₅₀ i.e. the concentration of test compound required to inhibit the growth of bacteria by 50% for **1** (44.3 µg/ml) and **2** (**2a**, 47.8 µg/ml; **2b**, 36.1 µg/ml; **2c**, 59.7 µg/ml; **2d**, 49.2 µg/ml) have been tested against

Fig. 3. Supramolecular construction in **2b** derivative by hydrogen bonding (NH \cdots O) and non-classical interaction S-O \cdots CH.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths and bond angles of **2b**

SMX-N=N-C₆H₂(*p*-OH)(*m*-OCH₃)(*m*-HC=N-C₆H₄(*p*-CH₃)) (**2b**)

	Bond length (Å)			Bond angle (°)	
	X-Ray	DFT		X-Ray	DFT
N(8)-N(9)	1.260(3)	1.281	N(8)-N(9)-C(36)	114.6(19)	116.4
C(33)-N(8)	1.419(3)	1.420	C(33)-N(9)-N(8)	113.3(19)	115.1
C(36)-N(9)	1.402(3)	1.413	N(9)-C(36)-C(37)	124.0(2)	124.5
C(26)-N(29)	1.309(3)	1.300	N(9)-C(36)-C(41)	115.7 (2)	115.3
N(10)-C(44)	1.402(3)	1.419	C(44)-N(10)-C(43)	128.6(19)	123.7
C(30)-S(2)	1.751(2)	1.870	N(10)-C(44)-C(45)	115.6(2)	117.5
C(43)-H(43)	0.950(3)	1.091	O(7)-S(2)-C(30)	108.9(10)	108.3

B. subtilis (ATCC 6633) and the results are much below the value of parent SMX (111.9 μ g/ml). The IC₅₀ of **2a-d** show that **2b** is more potent than that of the others. On the other hand -CHO is more polar and less space demanding than -CH=N-Ar and may also be easily permeable in the cell membrane. The inhibition profile is shown in Fig. 5. From the result it is evident that the drug mol-

ecules produce a concentration dependent decrease in the growth of both Gram-positive *B. subtilis* bacteria.

Theoretical interpretation by DFT and docking studies

The best pose docked phase interaction has been evaluated by docking score, binding energy and log P data. To account druglikeness property of

Fig. 4. Three different fashions of (CH... π) interactions in 2b.

Fig. 5. Anti-bacillus activity of SMX, 1, 2a-d on *Bacillus subtilis*.

the ligands Lipinski's rule of five^{34,35}, have been examined and toxicity has been evaluated by ADMET studies. The calculated data show the good solubility level, moderate absorption stage, seven or eight H-bond acceptors, two H-bond donors and follow Lipinski's filter. This implies that present series of azo-sulfonamids/azo-imino sulfonamids interact more strongly than that of SMX to DHPS

protein (Table 3). The hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts of the derivatives bind through hydrogen bonding and different electrostatic interactions³³.

Docking analyses indicate that the C-DOCKER interaction energy of the drugs with 3TZF follow the ordering 2a > 2c > 2d > 2b > 1. The steps of best interaction of the drug-to-protein are the

communication to surface interaction which follows the binding to penetration into the cavity or pocket and finally the chemical and physiological transformation through metabolic process³⁴. Hence C-DOCKER interaction energy trend does not reflect its binding strength; it is the binding energy which will reflect the strength of binding. The drug **2a** binds to the protein (Supplementary Materials, Table 1), 3TZF@**2a** and shows highest stability (-133.53 kcal/mol). The interaction proceeds

mainly through electrostatic path with 3TZF. The drug **1** interacts with 3TZF (3TZF@**1**) and the amino acid residues involve in the process are Gln149, Lys221, Ser61, Arg63. The amino acid residues Gln189, Lys221 for **2a**; Lys221, Thr62 for **2b**; Gly189 Leu194, Gln149 for **2c**; and Arg255, Lys221, Thr62 for **2d** are involved in the binding cavity of the protein (Table 3). Interaction analysis suggests that ligand **1** binds with DHPS of *E. coli* through oxygen atom of -SO₂,

Table 3. Details of interactions in most stable protein-ligand complex for **1** and **2a-d**

Compd.	Hydrogen bonds					π -bond			
	No. of H-bond	End 1	End 2	Bond distance (Å)	Angle \angle D-H-A (°)	Bond distance (Å)			
3TZF@ 1	3	Gln149 (NH)	Carbonyl O of <i>o</i> -vaniline	2.13	149	2.66	Thr62 NH to oxazole nucleus		
		Ser61 (OH)	N of oxazole	2.32	159				
		Arg63 (NH)	N of oxazole	2.96	115				
		Lys221 (HC)	O of SO ₂	2.70	123				
3TZF@ 2a	1	Gly189 (O=C)	HO of <i>o</i> -vaniline	2.21	91	4.58	Pro64 to benzene ring of <i>o</i> -vaniline		
		Lys221 (CH)	HO of SO ₂	2.68	118			3.76	Ser61 NH to oxazole nucleus
3TZF@ 2b	3	Lys221 (CH)	O of oxazole	2.09	145	3.97	Pro64 to benzene ring of SMX		
		Thr62 (OH)	SO ₂ of SMX	1.96	151				
		Thr62 (NH)	SO ₂ of SMX	2.14	150				
3TZF@ 2c	3	Gly189 (O)	OH of <i>o</i> -vaniline moiety	2.00	98	4.86	Phe28 nucleus to <i>o</i> -vaniline ring		
		Leu194 (NH)	O of oxazole moiety	2.84	113			4.40	Pro64 nucleus to <i>o</i> -vaniline ring
		Gln149 (NH)	N of oxazole moiety	3.38	144				
3TZF@ 2d	6	Arg255 (NH)	O of SO ₂ moiety	2.93	140				
		Arg255 (NH)	N of oxazole moiety	2.72	102				
		Arg255 (NH)	O of oxazole moiety	3.00	90				
		Lys221 (NH)	O of oxazole moiety	2.11	150				
		Thr62 (OH)	O of SO ₂ moiety	2.04	145				
		Thr62 (NH)	O of SO ₂ moiety	2.04	153				

oxazolyl moiety, azo-N and CHO moiety form recognizable H-bonds (Fig. 6). Gln149 NH atom interacts with -C=O of *o*-vaniline moiety: H-O 2.33 Å and \angle N-H---O, 149°; Ser61 OH atom interacts with N (oxazole moiety) : O-N, 2.32 Å and \angle O---H-N, 159°; Arg63 NH---N (oxazole) : H---N, 2.96 Å; \angle N-H---N, 115°; Lys221(CH---O of (SO₂)) : H---O, 2.21 Å; \angle C-H---O, 123° and, Thr61 NH nucleus involves π --- π interaction with oxazole ring

(2.66°) for **1** (Fig. 6) and Gly189 -C=O---H---O of *o*-vaniline, 2.21 Å; \angle O-H---C, 91°; Lys221 CH interacts with H of SO₂ moiety of SMX, O---H, 2.68 Å; \angle H---O---S 135° and Ser61 CH atom interacts with N (oxazole moiety), H---O, 2.38; \angle C-H---N, 164°, Thr62 (OH) interact with SO₂ of SMX moiety, H---O, 1.96 Å; \angle O-H---O, 145°, Ser61 NH nucleus involves π --- π interaction with oxazole ring (3.76°) for **2a** (Fig. 7); Lys221 CH

Fig. 6 . Best fit binding of **1** in the DHPS (PDB id 3TZF) cavity; (a) 2D interaction and (b) 3D interaction.

Fig. 7 . Best fit binding of **2a** in the DHPS (PDB id 3TZF) cavity; (a) 2D interaction and (b) 3D interaction.

Fig. 8. Best fit binding of **2b** in the DHPS (PDB id 3TZF) cavity; (a) 2D interaction and (b) 3D interaction.

Fig. 9. Best fit binding of **2c** in the DHPS (PDB id 3TZF) cavity; (a) 2D interaction and (b) 3D interaction.

interacts with O of oxazole moiety : H---O, 2.09°; \angle C---H---O 145°, Thr62 OH atom to O of SO₂ moiety of SMX H---O, 1.96 Å; \angle O-H---O, 151°; Thr62 NH atom to SO₂ moiety of SMX : H---O, 2.14 Å and \angle N---H---O, 150°; Pro64 NH nucleus involves π --- π interaction with benzene ring of SMX (3.97°) for **2b** (Fig. 8); Gly189 O atom interacts with OH of *o*-vaniline moiety : O---O, 2.00

Å; \angle O---O-H, 89°, Leu194 NH atom interacts with O of oxazole moiety : H---O, 2.84 Å and \angle N-H---O, 113°), Gln149 NH atom interacts with N of oxazole moiety : H---N, 3.38 Å and \angle N-H---N, 144°) and Pro64 NH nucleus involves π --- π interaction with benzene ring of *o*-vaniline (4.40°) for **2c** (Fig. 9); Arg255 NH atom interacts with O of SO₂ moiety, N of oxazolyl moiety, O of oxazole

Fig. 10. Best fit binding of **2d** in the DHPS (PDB id 3TZF) cavity; (a) 2D interaction and (b) 3D interaction.

moiety : H---O, 2.93 Å, H---N, 2.72 Å, H---O, 3.00 Å, and \angle N-H---O, 140°; \angle N-H---N, 102° (\angle N-H---O, 90°), Lys221 NH atom interact with O of oxazole moiety : H---O, 2.11 Å and \angle N-H---O, 150°), Thr62 OH atom to O of SO₂ moiety of SMX H---O, 2.04 Å; \angle O-H---O, 145°; Thr62 NH atom to SO₂ moiety of SMX : H---O, 2.04 Å and \angle N---H---O, 153°; for **2d** (Fig. 10).

Theoretical interpretation of electronic spectra

The DFT computation method is used to optimize the structure of the ligands. The bond distances and angles have been verified by the comparing between the DFT optimized and X-ray determined structures (Table 2). To simplify analysis of DFT computation result the structure of HL has been divided into azo, benzene sulfonamide (BSN), methyloxazolyl (MOX) and salicylaldehyde and aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-methoxyaniline (Supplementary Materials, Figs. 17–21). Theoretically generated structures of the ligands are used to calculate various data and energy of the functions. The electronic properties of these molecules have also been verified by DFT

data (Supplementary Materials, Tables 3–12). The HOMO of **1** is constituted by *o*-vaniline (79%), azo (7%), benzulfonamide (13%) and oxazole (1%), whereas **2a** is constituted by aniline (45%), azo (3%), benzulfonamide (5%), *o*-vaniline (47%); **2b** is constituted by toluidine (9%), azo (7%), benzulfonamide (08%), *o*-vaniline (76%); **2c** is constituted by *p*-chloroaniline (4%), azo (7%), benzulfonamide (9%), *o*-vaniline (80%); **2d** is constituted by *p*-methoxyaniline (37%), azo (5%), benzulfonamide (7%), *o*-vaniline (51%).

The electronic transitions have been explained by the population of occupied MOs and unoccupied MOs. The intensity of these transitions has been assessed from oscillator strength (*f*). The ligands show transitions between different molecular fragments, viz. HOMO → LUMO, 423.10 nm (*f*, 0.5044); HOMO-2 → LUMO, 336.5 nm (*f*, 0.5961) are considered as admixture of *o*-vaniline to benzulfonamide, azo charge transitions, whereas most of the accepted transitions (Supplementary Materials, Tables 3–12) are intra-ligand charge transfer transitions.

Conclusion

One of the wonder discoveries of the 20th century is Antibiotics. This is true, but the real wonder is the rise of antibiotic resistance in hospitals, communities, and the environment concomitant with their use. A series of novel azo-imine derivatives of sulfamethoxazole has been characterized. The microbial activity against *B. subtilis* shows that their efficiency is much better than parent SMX. The molecular docking study computationally proves the proficiency of these drugs based on fitting in the DHPS cavity of the protein.

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Supporting Information

Crystallographic data for the structure have been deposited to the Cambridge Crystallographic Data center, CCDC No. 1589015. These data can be obtained free of charge Via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>. or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk

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